

Recruitment and Selection Decisions of SMEs

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Dr. Iftikhar Ahmed Butt**, Assistant Professor, University of Management Sciences & Information Technology, Kotli AK Pakistan, post code: 11100 ⁽²⁾**Naveeda Zeb**, Lecturer and Academic Coordinator, University of Management Sciences & Information Technology, Kotli AK Pakistan, post code: 11100

Abstract

This research paper explores recruitment and selection process of Pakistani-owned SMEs in the UK. The study was aimed to discover some facts and figures about strategies of these enterprises in hiring and keeping right people with them. The overall investigation process was undertaken through a field survey around 100 respondents involved in recruitment decisions of these enterprises. These respondents were randomly selected from 50 enterprises located in major cities of the UK. To facilitate data gathering process a structured questionnaire comprising a wide range of close-ended questions was prepared and carefully distributed among selected respondents. The researcher did his best to ensure that data gathered through field survey was complete, correct and current. Analysis of the data revealed that majority of small companies preferred informal ways of testing and selecting people at all levels, particularly at administrative and operating levels. On the other hand, majority of medium companies preferred formal ways of recruitment at managerial level and mixed ways (both formal and informal) at lower levels. However, most recruitment and selection decisions were taken by owner managers of these companies. Findings of the study are expected to provide some useful guidelines to the UK based ethnic minority SMEs in general and Pakistani-owned SMEs in particular.

Key words: SMEs, Recruitment, Selection, EMBs, UK, Pakistan

1. Introduction

Recruitment and selection process plays a vital role in attracting, hiring and retaining talent to strengthen managerial and operational dimensions of organizations. Without qualified and competent manpower it is not possible for them to compete in the market and to keep pace with emerging challenges. As far as the UK is concerned, it is multi-cultural society with free market economy requiring multi-skilled people to survive, grow and compete in the market. Organizations whether they are large or small need to adopt effective recruitment process to ensure availability of knowledgeable and skilled people to achieve better performance. As far as small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are concerned, due to ever rising competition in this sector, they need to be more careful and vigilant in having right people with them. The case of Ethnic Minority Enterprises (EMBs) in the UK is more sensitive because of their limited resources to apply formal and organized procedures of testing people to facilitate suitable recruitments. Pakistani-owned SMEs are facing similar difficulties. Because of semiskilled and unskilled employees with them, they are facing some issues with regards to their adjustability in the UK's highly competitive business environment. However, a number of Pakistani-owned SMEs were found in better employment conditions. They had allocated reasonable budget to facilitate formal recruitment and selection procedures. Comparatively they were making good business with sustainable growth and development.

This paper was directed to investigate recruitment and selection strategies and practices of Pakistani-owned SMEs in the UK with ambition to discover some facts and figures about their recruitment and selection strategies and procedures. For this purpose 50 enterprises with 165 respondents were randomly selected from those areas of the UK which were thickly populated with Pakistani SMEs. To undertake data gathering process a field survey was conducted with the help of a semi-structured questionnaire comprising a wide range of close-ended and descriptive questions. The questionnaire was circulated among all selected respondents. To ensure maximum response, the respondents were approached through all means of communication including postal mails, emails, telephone and face to face meetings. The researcher was interested to cover majority of respondents with minimum target of 100 respondents. At the beginning response rate was very slow and only 30 % responses were received. However, with the help continuous contacts and reminders, the researcher succeeded in achieving minimum target of 100 respondents.

The analysis of the primary data gathered through field survey revealed that majority of these companies preferred organized and formal procedures of recruitment and selection at managerial level and informal at

administrative and operating levels. They were more concerned and careful while selecting managers, specialists and technicians. Formal tests and interviews were being undertaken to pick and choose suitable individuals for these positions. Most of hiring process for higher positions remained centralized with little influence from close relatives and friends. On the other hand hiring process at administrative and lower levels remained somewhat decentralized and majority of positions were being filled through references and recommendations. Medium enterprises were found more formal as compared with small enterprises. However, at lower levels a close similarity was found between small and medium enterprises. Both were found flexible and accommodating while taking people from working class. Majority of medium enterprises had allocated some budget for their recruitment and selection activities; whereas, small enterprises were rarely found with allocated budget for their hiring activities. Overall, majority of Pakistani-owned enterprises under survey were found with mix of formal and informal recruitment procedures according to the nature positions at various levels of operations. Findings of the study are expected to provide some useful information to newly built ethnic minority SMEs to streamline modalities of their recruitment and selection process.

2. Literature review

The literature reveals that most of the previous research in the UK on employer's recruitment procedures has mainly been concerned with large organizations; however, an increasing interest in SME research has been reported during the last few decades because of inability of large companies to generate sufficient job opportunities to overcome rising unemployment (Blackburn and Smallbone, 2008). In a similar vein, other research into SMEs suggests that the 'fit' of potential workers with the culture of the firm is important to SME employers and perceptions of not fitting in can develop behavior militating against the provision of equal employment opportunities among employers (Pittaway and Thedham, 2005). Research suggests that the existence of a personnel management or HR section might influence the recruitment process to make it less discriminatory for people from diverse backgrounds, enabling them to be short-listed and interviewed. Contrarily, an owner as employer type of businesses with no personnel or HR sections have been found not to recruit people they perceive will not make a seamless transition into the organization (Nunn et al., 2010).

Literature further reveals that despite important role of SMEs in the UK economy, relatively little is known about the process of decision-making within them regarding recruitment procedures (Blackburn and Smallbone, 2008). There is broad agreement that the labor market in Britain has undergone profound changes over the past quarter century, which have affected the nature and organization of paid work (Sunley et al., 2006). A major shift concerns that from manufacturing to services and while the rise of services has partly offset industrial decline, it has been accompanied by a growth in forms of flexible work. Many jobs in services involve 'nonstandard' forms of employment characterized by part-time working, temporary work, self-employment, home working, and shift work (Felstead and Jewson, 1999) Flexible labor markets are said to allow businesses to hire and fire staff according to the demand for products and services at different times (Floyd, 2003).

In recruitment process, the employment interview is by far the most frequently used employment selection and decision-making device in organizations (Kennedy, 1994). Eder and Harris (1999: 3) note that interviewer judgment can be influenced by a range of personal and political agendas. As they further state, companies can utilize employment interviews in quite different ways in the selection process, using them early on or later in the hiring process or using multiple interviews (Eder and Harris, 1999). Howard and Ferris (1996: 112) argue that the employment interview is influenced by the 'nonverbal and self-promotion behaviors of the applicant, interviewer training, and the requirements of the job'. Interviewers can also make 'early impressions' about candidates in an interview which will have little grounding in the candidate's ability to do the job in question. Some research suggests that interviewers reach decisions within the first four minutes of an interview (in Kennedy, 1994: 110). That employers have been found to make recruitment decisions in the first minutes of an interview lends weight to the thesis that recruiters can operate with stereotypes of 'idealized successful applicants against which real applicants are judged' (in Kennedy, 1994: 111). We might hypothesize that predetermined factors valued by employers might incorporate skills, gender, age or family circumstances, for

example, which may disadvantage some candidates more than others. Some of these factors may come into play in the short-listing stage where they are discernible from an application form or CV (quoted in Kennedy, 1994). The factors informing the recruitment decisions are represented diagrammatically in Figure 1, which displays a summary of a research report published by the department for work and pension (DWP) UK in 2011. Findings of the report were based upon a qualitative study (exploring employer's recruitment behavior and decisions) carried out by the University of York and the Social Policy Research Unit on behalf of the Department for Work and Pensions. The study conducted around a sample of 30 SME employers was supervised by Jacqueline Davidson a Research Fellow in the Social Policy Research Unit, University of York, working on the welfare and employment program. Some relevant findings the report are discussed as follows.

The recruitment process as depicted in Figure 1 below does not remain fixed and varies according to the nature, resources and requirements of SMEs. The report indicates that employers place different emphasis on the specifications of potential applicants, for example qualifications (technical and professional), skills (driving license, computer literacy) or attributes (presentable, hard-working). Furthermore, some employers prefer to specify main roles and responsibilities in their advertisements to deter irrelevant and unsuitable candidates to save the time. After generating a large pool of applications, it was found that a majority of employers in these companies used short listing procedures to screen out irrelevant applicants at initial stage of recruitment.

Figure1. SME employers' recruitment decisions

Source: Davidson, (2011)

The process can begin when potential applicants phone up or arrive at the employment premises to ask for an application form or to enquire about the job, when employers can ask them some very basic screening questions, such as their current position and experience and the reasons for applying for the job. Similarly, short-listing could also happen over the telephone when candidates phoned to enquire about a position. Examples here include employers being put off potential applicants because of their telephone manner, or lack

of experience or because of their English language skills. The short listing process helps in choosing comparatively a better quality of candidates and to proceed towards final selection (Davidson, 2011).

The interviews and practical tests (trial shifts) are frequently used by the employers. Some employers in SMEs use interviews in conjunction with trial shifts for chefs, health care assistants or technicians to evaluate their potential employees. Trial shifts were seen as useful by some employers as they allowed an assessment of both the candidate's abilities and their potential fit with the other staff. However, trial shifts were not used at all by some other employers because training was needed before the successful candidate could undertake the tasks required for the job. While there is a preference for informality, recruitment methods have also been shown to vary between industries and sectors. What is almost self-evident for SMEs is that because they have limited resources and fewer employees to begin with, it is extremely difficult for them to maintain or develop an internal labor market based on recruitment and career development (Taylor, 2010; Marlow, 2005). For most SMEs, recruitment of new staff is via closed and responsive methods (flexible and easily approachable methods such as walk-in interviews) that rely on informal networks (Carrol et al., 1999). The implications of how SMEs recruit people can lead to potential problems of discrimination. As highlighted in the literature, very few SMEs monitor their recruitment methods related to equal opportunities (Forth et al., 2006). Further problems can arise with an *ad hoc* and informal approach to recruitment. For example, indirect discrimination can be evident when workers are recruited from the same ethnic group or from within a particular familial and social milieu (Ram, 1991; Ram and Holiday, 1993).

In pragmatic terms many owner-managers find *word-of-mouth* recruitment to be a simple and cost effective method with virtually no or little consideration given to equal opportunities implications (Holliday, 1995). According to Carrol et al. (1999), word of mouth recruitment methods are potentially discriminatory. On the other hand, given the lack of in-house expertise in human resource management techniques and the nature of labor market, it could be argued that these methods are the most appropriate; hiring '*known quantities*' could be seen as a very effective way of reducing uncertainty in recruitment decisions.

With regards to application of generic HR functions (including recruitment, training and employment relations) a considerable diversity has been found in the ways of these practices are applied in SMEs. There is more use of recruitment and selection procedures in these companies compared to other functions. The factors such as nature of jobs, word of mouth recruitment or references play an important in the recruitment process of these companies. The use of formal applications, formalized job descriptions and selection processes are rarely in evidence in SMEs. However, some of these companies for some of their positions at higher level have been reported while using formal procedures (Davidson, 2011; Holliday, 1995).

3. Problem statement

Hiring and keeping talent is prerequisite for business organizations to cope with emerging challenges of the market. It is not possible to survive and grow in the market without motivated and competent manpower. Therefore, organizations need to be vigilant and careful in their recruitment decisions. This paper was directed to undertake an empirical investigation around Pakistani-owned SMEs in the UK to discover some facts and figures about recruitment strategies and practices of these enterprises. The ultimate objective of the study was to learn some lessons from experiences of these companies and make these lessons a source of guidance and motivation for other similar business entities of the UK.

4. Research objectives

- To investigate some important secondary sources generally about recruitment and selection approaches of SMEs in the UK to familiarize with findings of contemporary authors and researchers.
- To conduct empirical investigation around Pakistani-owned SMEs in the UK to get some primary facts and figures about recruitment and selection frameworks of these enterprises.
- To provide some guidelines to similar businesses in the light of derived findings and enabling them to refine their selection programs.

5. Methodology

5.1 Research design

The research design of any study is a framework of the research in action and can be exploratory, descriptive and/or explanatory (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Yin, 2009). This study is cross-sectional (by time horizon) and exploratory (by investigating and discovering ideas and facts about and gaining insight into the problem) in nature. Keeping in view subjective nature of the research topic the researcher preferred exploratory research design directed to gather a mix of qualitative and quantitative data through field survey undertaken with the help of a semi-structured questionnaire composed of a wide range of open and close-ended questions. To put the work at wider context, the respondents were chosen from different geographical backgrounds and different enterprises with different business perspectives.

5.2 Sampling

Sampling plays an important role in selecting a reasonable number of respondents with potential to represent whole target population. To execute sampling process, the researcher conducted an informal survey through emails, telephone calls and personal visits to get accurate information about Pakistani business community in the UK. The informal survey revealed that the most of Pakistani entrepreneurs are based in some specific counties of the UK. The following list provides name of these counties with number of respondents selected from each of these counties.

Names of counties	Number of respondents
1. Bedfordshire	45
2. Berkshire	36
3. Cambridgeshire	30
4. Essex	28
5. Lancashire	33
6. Nottinghamshire	25
7. South Yorkshire	20
8. Staffordshire	35
9. West Yorkshire	25
10. West Midlands	23
Total number of respondents	300

The researcher decided to approach all enterprises which were willing to participate in survey process. Hence questionnaire was circulated around 150 enterprises with 300 hundred respondents (two respondents from each company). However initial response rate was very low. After continuous efforts (reminders through emails, telephone calls, and personal visits) the researcher succeeded in achieving a minimum target of 50 companies and 100 respondents. The researcher did his best to cover enterprises with different businesses perspectives and located in different counties of the UK.

5.3 Contact methods

The questionnaire is one of the most widely used data collection techniques within the survey strategy where each respondent is asked to respond the same set of questions in a predetermined order (deVaus, 2002). It provides an efficient way of collecting precise responses to prescribed research questions from a large sample prior to quantitative or qualitative analysis (Bell, 2005). In questionnaire method the respondents can be accessed through internet, telephone, face to face meetings, postal mail and delivery and collection approaches to get the questionnaires filled by them. In this survey there was primary use of postal mail, face to face

meetings and delivery and collection approaches. After circulation of questionnaires, respondents were approached again through emails and telephone calls to motivate them for the completion and safe return of these questionnaires.

6. Findings

6.1 Small companies preferred informal recruitment: The empirical investigation revealed that a majority of small companies (23 out of 30; 70%) preferred informal ways to fill most of their vacant positions. Only 30% companies used a mix of formal (use of local news-papers, application forms, and also some sort of formal interviews and practical tests) and informal approaches (such as casual callers, approaching any interested individuals through employees, relatives and friends and informal interviews). They used formal approaches to select people at managerial and technical positions and informal approaches to select most of their working staff. 50 out of 60 (83%) respondents from these companies said that formal application forms, practical tests or formal interviews were rarely used and only around 15% used CVs to evaluate eligibility of interested applicants. Overall, 41 out of 60 (68 %) did not require CVs and totally depended upon references (from family and friends) and informal interviews. On the other hand 19 out of 60 (32%) respondents reported formal ways of recruitment, including the use of application form, formal interviews and practical tests for applicants. Sometimes small company proprietors select new employees on the basis of their '*personal judgment*' and even accept new recruits on '*word of mouth*' of the people known to them. In their opinion, people from family and friends are familiar to them. They already understand their ability and aptitude at work; therefore, recruitment from family and friends saved much of the time, efforts and resources that would be needed involving lengthy and formal procedures to recruit strangers. The table 1 below displays recruitment practices of small companies at a glance.

Table 1: Recruitment and selection process in small companies

Variables	The process of recruitment and selection
Vacancy announcement	Company notice board / vacancy notices at front door of the company, words of mouth.
Sources of recruitment	Internal and external (depending upon nature of the post and inside availability of relevant applicants).
Influences	Close relatives, friends and company employees
Applications	Black and white simple application forms, oral requests, CVs
Tests	Rare use of practical tests except for few technical posts
Interviews	Frequent use of informal interviews at company premises
References	Frequent use of references to ensure selection of trustworthy persons
Selection	Informal/oral, little use of appointment letters
Orientation/ induction	Informal orientation and induction without having any organized events
Agreement	Informal/oral, little use of any written agreement

Source: Primary data gathered through case studies

6.2 Medium companies preferred formal process: Unlike small companies, a majority of medium companies (16 out of 20; 80%) used entirely formal methods of recruitment and selection for all types of their employees (from top to bottom). As reported by 34 out of 40 (85%) respondents, these companies preferred to advertise their vacant positions in local news-papers, job centers and on company websites. To attract suitable candidates, formal (online and postal) applications were invited to facilitate the initial recruitment process. Thereafter, formal tests and interviews (according to the nature of the position) were conducted to make the final selection.

Few respondents (6 out of 40; 15%) reported using informal processes of recruitment and selection to fill vacant positions in their companies. As reported, to fill the lower level positions, quite a few companies adopted an informal process to save time and resources. The data further revealed that medium companies did not follow any hard and fast approach to employee recruitment. It depended upon the nature and requirements of the job to decide about a particular approach to recruitment. Normally, a formal lengthy procedure was adopted for higher positions; an informal and short-cut procedure was adopted for lower positions; whereas positions at middle level were filled through a mix of both procedures. The empirical investigation further reveals that degree of formality and informality varies from company to company depending upon personal visions and aptitudes of entrepreneurs/managers and variable nature and requirements of respective companies. Companies such as real estates, wholesale cash and carry and hotels and restaurants, etc. are more formal and organized in their recruitment process compared to such companies as retail outlets, cloth and fabrics, air-ticketing, cargo and insurance. In other words, formal or informal process of recruitment and selection of employees depended upon seniority of their roles. Table 2 gives a view of recruitment and selection process of medium companies.

Table 2: Recruitment and selection process in medium companies

Variables	The process of recruitment and selection
Vacancy announcement	Company notice board, local news papers, job centre
Sources of recruitment	Use of Internal and external sources depending upon nature and requirements of the posts to be filled. For example, to recruit people at higher positions external sources (e.g., Job centre, advertisement etc) are used; whereas, to recruit people at lower positions internal sources (e.g., word of mouth, company notice board etc) are preferred.
Influences	Less influence of family and friends or company employees on recruitment process compared to small companies
Applications	Formal applications, CVs
Tests	Practical tests (e.g., examining people through practical assignments related to their job) technical, managerial and administrative posts; no tests for low ranking positions
Interviews	Formal interviews by employers or managers of concerned departments for higher posts; informal interviews for low ranking positions. For higher positions in most cases a panel (comprising owner manager and head of concerned department) conducts interviews; whereas, for lower positions head of concerned department conducts these interviews. Only shortlisted (few in number) applicants are called for these interviews. Interview questions are prepared in advance with possibility of changes during interview. Time duration differs depending upon nature of different positions.
References	Required for each and every recruitment to ensure selection of trustworthy people
Selection	Formal appointment letters with brief description of job and work schedules
Orientation and induction	Formal orientation and induction events are conducted to introduce new comers about company, employees, and their roles and responsibilities
Agreements	Formal / written agreements with clear description of terms and conditions; however, these agreements remain informal / oral for low ranking recruitments

Source: Primary data gathered through case studies

6.3 Use of references: As highlighted by 41 out of 60 (68%) respondents from small companies, there was a frequent use of references in the recruitment process of these companies; whereas, 19 out of 60 respondents (32%) said that they did not use references. With regard to medium companies, majority of the respondents (26 out of 40; 65%) did not say that they used any references in the recruitment process of their companies; whereas 14 out of 40 (35%) acknowledged a clear role of references in the recruitment process of their companies.

6.4 The recruitment structure: According to 53 out of 60 respondents (88%) from small companies, the recruitment process remained centralized. Most of the recruitment decisions were taken by entrepreneurs/owner-managers in these companies; only 7 out of 60 (12%) respondents reported a decentralized structure where managers were authorized to recruit people on behalf of the entrepreneurs. In medium companies, overall recruitment structure remained mixed. As reported by 31 out of 40 respondents (78%), the recruitment process for technical and managerial positions was undertaken by the top management; whereas, positions at operating levels were filled by the department manager/supervisor concerned. Only 9 out of 40 (22%) respondents reported a centralized recruitment structure at all levels in their respective companies.

6.5 Employment agreements: Majority of the respondents in small companies, 48 out of 60 (80%) respondents reported informal employment agreements (oral/unwritten terms and conditions) in these companies; only 12 out of 60 (20%) respondents reported the use of formal agreements (written terms and conditions). The respondents stated that both parties feel comfortable with informal agreements. Unlike small companies, a majority of respondents from medium companies (24 out of 40; 60%) reported the use of formal (written terms and conditions) employment agreements for all types of their recruitment; 16 out of 40 (40%) respondents highlighted the simultaneous use of formal and informal (oral/unwritten) agreements. They remarked that formal or informal agreements depended upon the nature of the recruitment and the mutual requirement or convenience of both the parties. Table 3 below provides a comparative view of recruitment practices of these (both small and medium) companies.

Table 1: Recruitment practices of Pakistani-owned SMEs in the UK

No.	Variables	Small Companies Response (%)	Medium Companies Response (%)
1	Formal/informal recruitment	Informal 83 Formal 17	Informal 15 Formal 85
2	Recruitment structure	Centralized 88 Decentralized 12	Centralized 22 Decentralized 78
3	Employment agreement	Informal 80 Formal 20	Informal 40 Formal 60
4	Use of references	Use rate 85 No use 15	Use rate 35 No use 65
5	Recruitment tools	For majority of cases vacancy announcement at company notice board, informal interviews, CVs, references, casual callers at all levels.	For majority of cases advertisements (local news- papers, company website, job center, company notice board), applications, formal interviews, practical tests at all levels
6	Family/friends involvement	High involvement 75 Low involvement 25	High involvement 20 Low involvement 80

Source: Primary data gathered through field survey

6.6 Family members and/or friends involvement in the recruitment process: The involvement of family and friends had a direct influence on recruitment process of small companies. 45 out of 60 (75%) respondents clearly acknowledged the role of these factors in the recruitment process of these companies. It was identified that over 70% employees working in these companies were connected with the close relatives and friends of entrepreneurs/owner-managers of these companies. As suggested by 39 out of 60 (65%) respondents, these companies preferred to recruit people from family and friends because they were already well familiar with the employers concerned and it was felt that this should lead to an understanding between employers and employees. On the other hand, 15 out of 60 (25%) respondents mentioned that there was low involvement of family and friends in the recruitment process used in their companies. By contrast, medium companies were less influenced by family and friends' involvement in the recruitment process. They preferred to select people on merit basis, without any involvement of family or friends. As highlighted by 32 out of 40 (80%) respondents from these companies, most of the managerial, technical and administrative positions in these companies were filled through prescribed procedures. However, in the case of lower positions, they were flexible in accommodating family and friends because of the junior nature of the roles and responsibilities of these positions. By contrast 8 out of 40 (20%) participants highlighted a clear impact of family and friends in the recruitment process of these companies. The data further indicated that 16 out of 20 (80%) medium companies strictly followed a merit-based policy to fill their vacant positions.

Conclusion

The empirical investigation undertaken around 50 Pakistani-owned SMEs in the UK discovered some important facts and figures about recruitment and selection strategies and practices of these enterprises. Pakistani entrepreneurs are endeavoring hard to manage a knowledgeable and skilled workforce to grow and compete in the UK's multicultural business environment. They are applying some formal and organized approaches like application forms, tests and interviews to hire people for managerial, technical and administrative positions. However, they prefer to apply informal procedures like CVs, call-in interviews and references. A comparative analysis of the data reveals that medium companies are more organized and formal in their recruitment procedures as compared with small companies. Recruitment decisions of majority of small companies are under influence of close relatives, friends and references. 'Word of mouth' (references and recommendations) strategy is very common in these companies. Recruitment process in small companies remains centralized; whereas, medium companies prefer to keep the process centralized for higher positions and decentralized while hiring people for lower positions. Similarly, small companies prefer informal employment agreements; whereas, medium companies prefer formal agreements with written terms and conditions with selected employees. Diversity is lacking in both categories of enterprises. Majority of their employees belong to Asian-ethnic backgrounds. They prefer to hire them because they believe that Asian-ethnic employees are multi-lingual and can serve better to the customers with similar backgrounds. The overall analysis of the data reveals that Pakistani-owned SMEs in the UK are gradually improving their recruitment approaches and procedures to have skilled and motivated workforce to effectively compete in the market. They are diverting from 'word of mouth' strategy to formal recruitments through tests and interviews to pick and choose right individuals from available staff of job seekers. Pakistani entrepreneurs are moving forward to have people from diverse background to become mainstream companies while serving customers from multi-ethnic backgrounds. They are performing their role as bi-cultural mediators to ensure more and more acceptability and adjustability in the UK's multi-cultural business environment.

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